

INFLUENCER MARKETING AND PRODUCT ATTRACTIVENESS AS KEY DRIVERS TO GEN Z'S PURCHASE INTENTION

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ABSTRACT

Understanding what drives Gen Z's purchases is crucial in today's social media-driven world. This study examined the influence of influencer marketing and product/service attributes of Gen Z's purchase intention in a private sectarian institution. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, the study assessed participants' perceptions of influencer marketing considering authenticity, popularity, credibility, and quality of content, alongside product/service attributes namely: attractiveness and online reviews. It further explored the relationships between these variables. The participants of the study were 317 college students from a private sectarian institution who were randomly selected; all of whom were frequent users of social media. The study utilized the Influencer Marketing Questionnaire, adapted from Zniva et al. (2023), Zhao and Li (2023), and Rodrigues et al. (2024). It also included the Product/Service Questionnaire developed by Soler-Anguiano et al. (2022) and Kevin et al. (2020). The Purchasing Intentions Questionnaire was adopted from Zhou and Wang (2023), Nadanyiova & Sujanska (2023), and Pinto and Paramita (2021). Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the participants' profiles, while correlation and regression analyses were applied to test the significance of relationships among variables. Findings indicate that popularity and quality of content emerged as the primary drivers of purchase intention. Popularity, being the most significant factor, demonstrated that participants are highly influenced by well-known and widely followed influencers, while high-quality content effectively captured their attention and sustained engagement. Moreover, online reviews, and attractiveness significantly influenced participants' purchasing decisions, highlighting the importance of peer feedback and the visual or functional appeal of a product in shaping Gen Z's purchase behavior. These results emphasize the critical role of both influencer marketing

dimensions and product/service characteristics in driving purchase intention. The study underscores the critical role of leveraging influencer marketing and enhancing product/service attractiveness to effectively engage Gen Z consumers. It offers actionable insights for marketers and businesses to tailor their strategies to this demographic, emphasizing authentic interactions and compelling product offerings to foster stronger purchase intentions.

Keywords: *Influencer marketing, product/service, purchase intention, Gen Z, social media*

INTRODUCTION

The development of the internet has revolutionized lives in ways that people never imagined. Social media usage is widespread and has been shown to influence the lives of Gen Z profoundly. Through social media platforms, people can connect with others globally and access digital content without time or location constraints. The rise of social media influencers in the digital realm signifies a remarkable difference from conventional celebrities who achieve fame via television or movies. Through their active participation in content creation across several social media platforms, influencers have developed sizable followings and wield considerable influence. These influencers are well-known for their ability to create engaging and intriguing films, and they can draw in a wide range of viewers from different backgrounds and age ranges (Barta et al., 2023). Influencer marketing has become a common strategy used by companies to market their goods and services. The term “influencer marketing” has become increasingly popular as a component of marketing communications strategies for brands across a range of product categories.

Companies hoping to expand their clientele and establish enduring relationships with them are adopting this approach (Aramburu & Pescador, 2019). Because they deliberately choose to follow these influencers, consumers are more likely to believe and embrace their point of view (Gomes et al., 2022). Since customers do not view influencer marketing as advertising, it is viewed as an innovative and cost-effective marketing tactic (Ye et al., 2021). It is an essential component of the business’s digital marketing strategy, which draws in highly engaged consumers and cutting-edge brands (Wiedmann & von Mettenheim, 2020). Users find the influencers to be more reliable as a result. Businesses and companies use them to market goods and services because of their broad appeal and capacity to reach large audiences. According to Ki et al. (2020), there is a developing relationship between followers and influencer networks. This attachment helps influencers market and promote enterprises more successfully.

Social media platforms including Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube are the main tools used in this kind of marketing. People with a substantial fan base from other users are considered social media influencers. By blending individual experiences with pertinent knowledge, they create the illusion that their audience is familiar with them

(Lou & Yuan, 2019). The absence of focused research into how influencer marketing affects Gen Z's purchasing intentions within private sectarian institutions is the study's research gap. Existing research might focus more broadly on consumer behavior or influencer marketing but may not delve into this particular demographic or institutional setting. For instance, Mavely (2023) revealed that most Gen Z customers believe suggestions from micro-influencer marketing tactics aimed at this group. The study, however, does not particularly discuss the setting of private sectarian institutions. Thus, this study aims to bridge this gap by providing insights into an underexplored area of influence marketing's efficacy within this specific context. Furthermore, the study examined the efficacy of influencer marketing and its product attractiveness, mainly influencers' authenticity, popularity, credibility, and quality of content including product attractiveness and online reviews, and their influence on Gen Z's purchasing intentions.

The growing reliance of customers on social media and their preference for online recommendations and reviews when making purchasing decisions have significantly contributed to the popularity of influencer marketing. Therefore, the primary goal of this study is to examine the extent to which influencer marketing influences the purchasing intentions of Gen Z students enrolled in a private sectarian institution.

Research Questions

The study determined the influence of influencer marketing, and product attractiveness as the key drivers of Gen Z's purchasing intention in a private sectarian institution. Specifically, the study sought to address the following research questions:

1. What is the participants' assessment of the influencer marketing in terms of:
 - 1.1 Influencers' Authenticity
 - 1.2 Influencers' Popularity
 - 1.3 Influencers' Credibility
 - 1.4 Quality of Content
2. What is the participants' assessment of the product/service in terms of:
 - 2.1 Attractiveness
 - 2.2 Online Reviews
3. What is the participants' level of purchasing intention?
4. Is there a significant relationship between influencer marketing and product/service in the participants' purchasing intention?
5. Do influencer marketing and product/service significantly influence the participants' purchasing intention?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive correlational research design, which was deemed appropriate for examining the influence of influencer marketing and product/service as key drivers of Gen Z's purchase intentions. The participants of the study were 317 college students from a private sectarian institution who were randomly selected; all of whom

were Gen Z and frequent users of social media. The study utilized the Influencer Marketing Questionnaire, adapted from Zniva et al. (2023), Zhao and Li (2023), and Rodrigues et al. (2024). It also included the Product/Service Questionnaire developed by Soler-Anguiano et al. (2022) and Kevin et al. (2020). The Purchasing Intentions Questionnaire was adopted from Zhou and Wang (2023), Nadanyiova & Sujanska (2023), and Pinto and Paramita (2021). Descriptive statistics such as means, percentage, frequency, and standard deviation were employed to organize the profile of the study. Pearson's correlation coefficient was applied to explore the linear relationships between influencer marketing, product/service, and purchasing intention. Multiple Regression Analysis was used to investigate the influence of influencer marketing and product or service on purchasing intention.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the participants' assessment of influencer marketing in terms of Authenticity, Popularity, Credibility, and Quality of Content?

The summary table provides participants' assessment of influencer marketing across four dimensions: authenticity, popularity, credibility, and content quality. Authenticity garnered a mean score of 3.82 (SD = 0.78), denoting that participants generally recognize influencers as relatable and genuine in their presentations. Such a finding aligns with Audrezet, de Kerviler, and Moulard's (2020) which highlight that authenticity contributes to positive audience perceptions. Popularity, with a moderate mean score of 3.37 (SD = 0.91), suggests that while participants recognize the value of having a large follower base, it is not seen as the defining characteristic of effective influencer marketing. This implies that an influencer's reach alone does not guarantee meaningful engagement or audience trust. Shan et al. (2020) emphasize that prioritizing popularity, such as focusing solely on follower counts, may divert attention from more critical attributes like credibility and authenticity. This underscores the need for a balanced approach, where popularity is considered alongside other significant qualities that resonate with audiences and foster genuine connections.

Credibility emerged as the highest-rated dimension, with a mean score of 4.30 (SD = 0.75). Participants' responses disclosed that influencers perceived as trustworthy and knowledgeable are highly regarded. Jin et al. (2019) point out that credibility enhances the audience's acceptance of influencers in marketing contexts. When influencers are seen to be true and reputable, customers are more likely to believe them, and this view affects their purchasing intention. This is following Gray Geppert's (2019) description of influencers as credible social media experts who establish their reputation by engaging with their audience in a meaningful way and conveying sincere messages. This research supports Nguyen et al. (2022) claim that trustworthy, interesting, and informative information is essential for establishing a connection with younger consumers. Additionally, content quality, was rated next to the highest with a mean of 4.06 (SD = 0.84), reflects the importance participants place on well-produced and engaging

materials. This finding resonates with Schouten et al. (2020) who found that high-quality content contributes to better audience reception and overall appreciation of influencer marketing.

The data further reveal that participants generally rated influencers' authenticity as high, with an overall mean score of 3.82. Such a finding implies that while the majority perceive influencers as authentic, there is notable variability in opinions among participants. According to Audrezet et al. (2020), authenticity and integrity are crucial elements that enhance an influencer's ability to engage with their audience and build trust effectively.

Table 1

Participants' Assessment of Influencer Marketing in terms of Authenticity, Popularity, Credibility, and Quality of Content

Participants' Assessment of the Influencer Marketing	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Authenticity	3.82	High	.78
Popularity	3.37	Moderate	.91
Credibility	4.30	High	.75
Quality of Content	4.06	High	.84
OVERALL MEAN	3.89		

Nevertheless, the data show that the participants rated the influencers' popularity as moderate as indicated by the overall mean of 3.37. This implies that only a small percentage of the population considers influencers to be particularly powerful in marketing contexts, even if they are typically regarded as moderate. Although a wide range of engagement levels is usually seen in marketing scenarios, the results are consistent with research like Lou and Yuan (2019), which highlights that the perceived popularity of influencers has a bearing on purchase intention. The overall mean score of 3.89 indicates that participants generally view influencer marketing in a favorable light, especially when key attributes such as credibility, authenticity, and content quality are present.

Research Question 2. What is the participants' assessment of the product/service in terms of Attractiveness and Online Reviews?

Table 2 revealed that the participants gave products or services high ratings for attractiveness, with an overall mean score of 4.30, which is interpreted as "High. Simms (2019) highlights that one of the most important aspects of marketing tactics is the appearance of the product, including components like packaging and design.

Table 2

Participant's Assessment of the Product/Service in terms of Attractiveness and Online Reviews

Participants' Assessment of the Product/Service	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Attractiveness	4.30		High
Online Reviews	4.44		High
Overall Mean	4.37		

Additionally, characteristics like product quality, distinctiveness, and performance are crucial in defining a product's appeal and capacity to draw in customers (Lutfie & Marcelino, 2020). These findings highlight the need for influencers and marketers to give products' aesthetic and practical appeal top priority to increase buyer curiosity and engagement. Moreover, the "High" interpretation is supported by the overall mean of 4.44, which highlights how important online reviews are in customer perceptions. These results are consistent with research showing how important online reviews are when consumers are making purchases. Consumers are increasingly using social media and online reviews to evaluate products or services, and they frequently value customer feedback more than direct business communication (Meijerink & Schoenmakers, 2020). According to Guo et al. (2020), thorough online reviews greatly increase purchase intentions because of their reliability of them. These studies are supported by the data in Table 6, which demonstrates the significant influence of online reviews in influencing participants' viewpoints and highlighting the significance of customer feedback in marketing tactics.

Research Question 3. What is the participants' level of extent of purchasing intention?

Table 3 shows an overall mean of 3.45 indicating a *moderate* purchasing intention implying that although individuals are somewhat motivated to purchase products or services, variables other than their immediate intentions probably have interplay with their decisions. These results correspond with Andreani et al. (2021) assertion that consumer demands drive purchasing intentions, which are influenced by beliefs and views toward products and services. Furthermore, Gupta (2021) pointed out that influencer marketing is essential in influencing consumer's intentions to buy by giving them important information about products, marketing, and market trends. According to Zak et al. (2020), the data's moderate purchasing intention might also reflect the significance of perceived genuineness and product trust, both of which are critical components in turning intention into action.

Table 3

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the participants' level of extent of purchasing intention

Dependent Variable	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Purchase Intention	3.45	Moderate	.86

Research Question 4. Is there a significant relationship between influencer marketing and product/service in the participants' purchasing intention?

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between influencer marketing, and product/service in the participants' purchasing intention.

Table 4 shows a highly significant correlation between the variables of influencer marketing, products/services, and purchasing intention leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Influencer marketing and purchase intention were found to be strongly positively correlated ($R=0.739$), indicating that participants' propensity toward purchasing increases in combination with influencer marketing's efficacy. Furthermore, it was shown that influencer marketing and products/services had a positive correlation ($R=0.713$), underscoring the connection between marketing strategies and product or service value. There was also a positive correlation between products/services and purchasing intention ($R=0.605$), suggesting that attractive and well-presented materials greatly influence consumers' decisions to make purchases. An improvement in one variable affects a rise in the others, according to the positive correlation coefficients, which imply that the variables fluctuate together and move in the same direction. These results are in line with Groen's (2020) claim that to build trust and influence consumer behavior, online marketing requires interesting and believable material. In a similar vein, Argyris et al. (2020) emphasized that marketing efforts are enhanced by the quality of products and services, resulting in an effect that increases purchase intentions.

Table 4

Correlation Coefficients of Result of Influencer Marketing, Products/Service, and Purchasing Intention

		Influencer Marketing	Products/Service
Influencer Marketing	Pearson Correlation	-	.713
	P - Value	-	.000
Products/Service	Pearson Correlation	.713	-
	P - Value	.000	-
Purchase Intention	Pearson Correlation	.739	.605
	P - Value	.000	.000
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Research Question 5. Do influencer marketing and product/service significantly influence the participants' purchasing intention?

Ho2. *The participants' assessments of influencer marketing, and product/service do not significantly influence their purchasing intention.*

Table 11 presents the Multiple Linear Regression results to test the influence of independent variables (Influencer Marketing and Product/Service) on the dependent variable (Purchase Intention). This determined if influencer marketing and product/service have a significant influence on the purchasing intention of the participants.

The regression analysis demonstrates the influence of influencer marketing and product/service attributes on participants' purchasing intention leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The model explains a substantial proportion of the variance ($R^2 = 0.643$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.636$, $F = 92.860$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that these predictors collectively accounting for 63.6% of the variability in purchasing intention. This suggests that 36.4% of the variance remains unexplained by the predictors in this model, implying that other factors, such as personal preferences, economic conditions, social influences, or brand loyalty, may also contribute to purchasing intentions. Previous literature, such as that Ferreira et al. (2022), emphasizes the role of psychological and situational factors, like attitudes, emotions, and peer pressure, in shaping consumer behavior. These additional variables might warrant further exploration to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of purchasing intention. Among the dimensions of influencer marketing, influencer's popularity ($\beta = 0.466$, $p < 0.001$) emerges as the most significant factor, affirming previous literature suggesting that influencers with a high follower count or widespread recognition tend to have a stronger impact on consumer behavior (Munnukka et al., 2019). This finding supports the idea that popularity enhances an influencer's ability to disseminate information effectively and reach a larger audience, thereby shaping purchasing intentions.

Table 5. Regression Analysis to determine the Influence of Influencer Marketing and Product/Service on Participants' Purchasing Intention

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		p
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-Value	
(Constant)	-.405	.234		-1.729	.085
Influencer's Authenticity (IA)	.115	.052	.104	2.228	.027
Influencer's Popularity (IP)	.423	.037	.466	11.391	.000
Influencer's Credibility (IC)	-.090	.053	-.078	-1.712	.088

Influencer's Quality of Content (IQC)	.237	.057	.228	4.183	.000
Product/Service Attractiveness (PA)	.184	.058	.159	3.188	.002
Product/Service Online Reviews (POR)	.165	.058	.118	2.836	.005

Model Summary

R = .802 R² = .643 Adjusted R² = .636 F-Value = 92.860 p = .000

**significant at 0.01 level

$$\text{Equation model: PI} = -.405 + .115\text{IA} + .423\text{IP} + -.090\text{IC} + .237\text{IQC} + .184\text{PA} + .165\text{POR}$$

Similarly, influencer's quality of content ($\beta = 0.228$, $p < 0.001$) plays a significant role, aligning with studies by Lou and Yuan (2019), which emphasize that engaging, creative, and high-quality content fosters trust and increases the likelihood of consumer action. The significance of quality content highlights the need for influencers to craft visually appealing and relevant posts that resonate with their audience. Additionally, influencer's authenticity ($\beta = 0.104$, $p = 0.027$) positively influences purchasing intention, consistent with findings by Audrezet et al. (2020), who argue that genuine and relatable influencers create deeper connections with their followers, making their recommendations more persuasive. Interestingly, influencer's credibility ($\beta = -0.078$, $p = 0.088$) does not significantly influence purchasing intention in this study.

This finding runs contrasts with prior research, such as Chavda and Chauhan (2024), which posits that credibility, encompassing expertise and trustworthiness, is a crucial determinant of persuasive communication. The non-significance of credibility might suggest that Gen Z consumers prioritize popularity, authenticity, and quality of content over perceived expertise when forming purchase intentions, reflecting their preference for relatable and engaging influencers. For product/service attributes, product attractiveness ($\beta = 0.159$, $p = 0.002$) significantly impacts purchasing intention. This finding aligns with Gou et al. (2020), emphasis on the role of product design and visual appeal in influencing consumer preferences. Products that are aesthetically pleasing or are aligned with consumer lifestyles are more likely to be purchased.

Additionally, online reviews ($\beta = 0.118$, $p = 0.005$) significantly predict purchasing intention, echoing studies by Osman and Ying (2022), which highlight the importance of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) in shaping consumer perceptions. Positive online reviews not only validate product quality but also reduce uncertainty, thereby fostering greater purchasing confidence. Overall, the results underscore the combined influence of influencer marketing and product/service attributes on Gen Z's purchasing intention. While influencer popularity and quality of content are particularly impactful, the findings also emphasize the importance of visually attractive products and positive customer feedback. These results provide valuable insights for marketers aiming to optimize influencer collaborations and product presentations to align with the preferences and

behaviors of Gen Z consumers. The findings also highlight the evolving nature of credibility, suggesting that it may be less critical for younger consumers who value relatability and engagement.

Conclusions

The results of this study validate the foundational theories of influencer marketing and product/service aspects in influencing Gen Z's purchasing intentions. Influencer marketing is consistent with important theories that highlight how perceived authenticity, popularity, credibility, and content quality affect the purchasing decisions of consumers. Together these elements lend support to the notion that social media influencers work as reliable middlemen, using their visibility, knowledge, and relatability to persuade their audience. This is consistent with source credibility theory, which holds that a communicator's persuasiveness is greatly influenced by their dependability, expertise, and competence.

In a similar vein, social proof theory serves as the foundation for the qualities of products and services, such as their attractiveness and online reviews. Attractiveness influences opinions of quality and desirability by reflecting how well products and services satisfy customer expectations both aesthetically and functionally. Online reviews, meanwhile, show how other people's opinions might influence how consumers act in a way. According to the social proof theory, people based on the recommendations as well as experiences of others, including reviews. This lessens uncertainty, fosters trust, and increases assurance in their intention to purchase. When taken as a whole, these characteristics demonstrate how crucial the product's appeal as well as other opinions are in influencing customer decision-making.

The study emphasizes that Gen Z may be effectively engaged and their purchase intentions increased through the strategic integration of influencer marketing dimensions (authenticity, popularity, credibility, and quality of content) and product/service dimensions (attractiveness and online reviews). This finding confirms the relevance of Source Credibility Theory and Social Proof Theory in understanding and shaping consumer behavior in the context of modern digital marketing.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion and the significance of the study, the following recommendations are formulated.

1. That business owner may...

1.1 Collaborate with influencers who share the brand's values and understand Gen Z's preferences and choose influencers with integrity, sincerity, and with the ability to produce engaging and relatable content to encourage purchase intentions.

1.2 Invest in better product design, quality, packaging, and branding and utilize emotional appeal and emphasize attributes that reflect Gen Z's values, as these are important determinants of purchase intention.

1.3 Address areas with moderate ratings, such as enhancing product branding and ensuring visually appealing content and strengthen the connection between branding elements (e.g., logos, packaging) and product quality to improve overall attractiveness.

2. That Influencers may...

2.1 Develop captivating, interactive videos, reels, and narratives using platforms such as YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok. Focus on improving areas like credibility and clarity, as moderate ratings in these aspects indicate room for growth.

2.1 Enhance content quality by integrating visually appealing and innovative elements to attract and engage audiences more effectively.

3. That Gen Z consumers may...

3.1 Make more informed, value-driven decisions by engaging with reliable influencers who align with your interests and values.

4. That Future Researchers may...

4.1 Expand on this study by exploring specific topics such as the influence of different content formats on purchase intention, the relative effectiveness of micro- and macro-influencers, and the long-term effects of influencer marketing.

4.2 Examine factors such as emotional involvement, trust, and the evolving role of social media in purchasing decisions to address the complexity of consumer behavior.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In regards to the Belmont Report's ethical guidelines, which Amdur and Bankert (2021) reference, the researcher followed specific guidelines and procedures during the investigation. First, in adherence to the guidelines of respect for persons, before the commencement of data collection, the administrator at the institution was formally consulted. This way, the participants were not only ensured to be treated as autonomous human beings but also to be told that they were forming a part of a study. Second, the survey instrument was administered only after in-house approval from the Research Ethics Committee of the school as well as the Institution to ensure beneficence. Their experience may have also shed some light on how influencer marketing affects the purchase intentions of participants, and the participants may have a better grasp of their consumer behavior because of their involvement. They also affect future marketing strategies that may be beneficial to both companies and consumers as well. Concerning risk, the researcher reported no change in risk their than the time to complete the questionnaire. This process minimizes risks to participants while maximizing benefits by ensuring that participation is voluntary and informed. Finally, the principle of justice was maintained in that written consent was obtained, and procedures were equal for the selection of participants. Following these ethical principles showcased the researcher's responsibility to conduct the study with integrity and protect the rights and welfare of the participant, as advocated by the Belmont Report. Everything was explained to the participants, including the purpose of the study, and they could ask for a summary of the

results, thereby further increasing their knowledge and awareness of the impact of influencer marketing.

With caution, the researcher submitted the ethical protocols for the data gathering proceeded to distribute the questionnaires to the target participants, and prepared the data for analysis.

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